

PREDICTING THE SEVERITY OF PERITONEAL COMPLICATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH PERFORATION OF HOLLOW ORGANS

F.M. Ismailov¹, K.F. Zuparov²

Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute^{1,2}

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14796257>

Abstract. *The article suggests that this method is suitable for predicting the course of peritoneal complications in patients with perforation of hollow organs. A study of risk factors influencing the treatment outcome was conducted, and an assessment system based on clinical and laboratory data was proposed. The results of the study may be useful for choosing treatment tactics and improving the effectiveness of medical care for patients.*

As part of the study, a prognostic model was developed that allows patients to be classified into risk groups (low, medium, and high) based on clinical and laboratory indicators such as CRP levels, leukocytes, hemoglobin, and coagulation parameters. The model enables a personalized approach to each patient, facilitates the recognition of those at high risk of complications such as sepsis and multiple organ failure, and allows for appropriate measures to be taken for recovery.

When applying this model in clinical practice, measures are taken to reduce mortality and optimize the use of medical resources.

Keywords: *peritonitis, sepsis, CRP (C-reactive protein), fibrinogen.*

Relevance. Perforation of hollow organs, such as the stomach, intestines, and gallbladder, is an urgent condition requiring immediate surgical intervention. Peritonitis, as a complication of perforation, is characterized by high mortality, especially when diagnosed late and in the event of complications [3].

Predicting the severity of peritoneal complications allows for monitoring the patient's condition, selecting the optimal treatment strategy, and preventing the development of adverse outcomes [1]. Modern approaches to prediction are based on the analysis of medical, laboratory, and instrumental data, which makes it possible to identify groups and personalize risks [4].

However, the accuracy of the prognosis depends on several factors, including the time of patient admission, the severity of the underlying disease, and the presence of comorbidities [2].

The development of objective prognostic models allows for improved diagnosis and the selection of the most effective treatment strategy for each patient.

Objective: The development and implementation of a prognostic model based on objective clinical and laboratory data aimed at optimizing the diagnostic processes and determining the treatment strategy for peritoneal surgeries.

Materials and Methods. The study included 60 patients aged 40 to 65 years, with a mean age of 52.0±1.22 years. Perforation of the stomach, small or large intestine, or gallbladder, confirmed by ultrasound (US), computed tomography (CT), and hospitalized in the surgical department of the 7th City Clinical Hospital between 2022 and 2024.

Stages of the study: Data collection (CRP levels, leukocytes, creatinine), surgical intervention (determining the volume of peritoneal effusion), postoperative monitoring (tracking complications).

Results and Discussion. Out of 63 patients, 18 (29%) developed severe complications, including sepsis. The main prognostic factors were: time from symptom onset to hospitalization (>24 hours), CRP level above 100 mg/L, and shock state upon admission (BP <90 mm Hg).

During the study, data from patients with perforation of hollow organs and the development of peritoneal changes were analyzed. Among the comorbid factors playing a key role in predicting the severity of the disease, the following were identified:

- Leukocytosis – an increase in the white blood cell count was observed in all patients with peritonitis, confirming the development of an inflammatory process and the infectious nature of the diseases. In patients with more pronounced symptoms of peritonitis, the leukocyte count was significantly higher, indicating a more severe course of the disease.

- Hematocrit and hemoglobin levels – anemia or significant changes in these indicators may suggest hypovolemia, which contradicts the prognosis.

- Coagulation parameters – such as fibrinogen level, prothrombin time, and international normalized ratio (INR). Coagulation disorders can pose risks for the patient related to coagulopathies, especially in cases of perforation and peritonitis.

The developed model effectively identifies risk groups:

- Low risk: Relatively satisfactory condition, minimal inflammatory changes (this group included 20 patients).

- Medium risk: Moderate inflammatory reaction, elevated CRP levels (25 patients).

- High risk: The presence of sepsis and multiple organ failure (18 patients) (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Distribution of patients into risk groups.

Among the 63 patients, the distribution into risk groups was accompanied by the following indicators:

Low risk: CRP <10 mg/L, absence of signs of sepsis or multiple organ failure, normal blood pressure (BP >90 mmHg), moderately elevated leukocyte count ($12-15 \times 10^9/L$), normal hemoglobin levels (135-160 g/L in men and 120-140 g/L in women), and slightly altered fibrinogen levels (from 0.2 to 1.3 ng/mL).

Medium risk: CRP 10–100 mg/L, signs of moderate inflammatory response, potential deterioration of condition if left untreated, but without shock, BP between 90–100 mmHg, elevated leukocyte count ($20-30 \times 10^9/L$ or higher), hemoglobin levels <120 g/L in women and <130 g/L in men, fibrinogen levels ranging from 1.3 to 5.9 ng/mL.

High risk: CRP >100 mg/L, presence of sepsis or multiple organ failure, shock (BP <90 mmHg) upon admission, delayed hospitalization for more than 24 hours from the onset of symptoms. Leukocyte count remains normal or even decreased due to depletion of the body's protective reserves, hemoglobin level <100 g/L, fibrinogen level >5.9 ng/mL (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Indicators of the group

The results of the study confirmed the importance of early diagnosis and prompt intervention. High levels of CRP and the presence of shock are key predictors of unfavorable outcomes. Elevated CRP levels indicated active stress and were associated with more severe forms of the disease.

Thus, the use of the developed prognostic model in clinical practice aims to reduce mortality and ensure the quality of treatment for patients with perforation of hollow organs. The model allows for the precise determination of treatment tactics and the allocation of resources for the priority treatment of patients with low complication risks.

REFERENCES

1. Абдумажидов А. Ш. и др. Лечение больных с инфицированными полостными образованиями печени раствором декасан //Новый день в медицине. – 2020. – №. 2. – С. 285-289.

2. Агзамова, М. Н., Исмоилов, Ф. М., Усаров, А. М., & Зупаров, К. Ф. (2020). Fatal cases analysis of patients with destructive forms of acute pancreatitis. *Новый день в медицине*, (2), 290-292.
3. Агзамова, М. Н., Тухтамурод, З. З., Акрамова, И. А., Исмаилов, Ф. М., & Зупаров, К. Ф. (2018). Изучение микробной флоры при перитонитах // *Молодой ученый*, (1), 33-34.
4. Турсуметов А., Сабирматов А., Исмаилов Ф. Экспериментальное обоснование эффективности фотодинамической терапии при распространенном перитоните // *Журнал биомедицины и практики*. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 206-215.